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Email: binasbookers2013@gmail.com

HELENE C. MAZZEO, MBA

Instructor III

Negros Oriental State University

Helenemazzeo53@gmail.com

“A WORLD WITHOUT YOU”

I cannot bear the thought of watching you leave.
So I look away, unaffected by what I can't see.
If I open my eyes, will you still look at me
with the same liveliness and love that I perceived?
Back in the fake world that I foolishly believed.

Afraid of what I'll find,
I cast myself aside.
Outside of the spotlight,
waiting in the sidelines.
Where I cling, so desperately,
to the home I reside.

I've turned my gaze again, forever repeating.
Trying to ground myself in a world that's always spinning.
But even when I try to pretend,
No matter how many times I get up I'll always fall back down again.

Someone will wake eventually,
Though it won't be you.
I open my eyes finally,
And I state back at reality
To the new world without you.